

CONDITIONS FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Giyasova Umida Erkinovna

Lecturer, Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

umidagiyasova@rambler.ru

Abstract: *The paper is devoted to the issue of analyzing of current conditions for improving the quality of education in the process professional development. The main goal of professional development courses is to ensure and establish confidence in each trainee about his/her ability to think creatively, to regularly encourage their creative activities. The importance of andragogical education is mentioned in the article because the pedagogical process in adult education is a process organized based on the interests and needs of subjects, in which the specific level of educational goals and the practical aspect of knowledge acquisition are considered as the primary criteria.*

Key words: *blended learning model, professional development courses, higher educational institutions' pedagogical personnel, andragogical education, andragogical model of teaching, ICT, trainee, quality improvement, distance learning.*

MALAKA OSHIRISH JARAYONIDA TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING SHART-SHAROITLARI

Giyasova Umida Erkinovna

O'qituvchi, Nizomiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti

umidagiyasova@rambler.ru

Annotatsiya: *Maqola malaka oshirish jarayonida ta'lim sifatini oshirishning hozirgi sharoitlarini tahlil qilish masalasiga bag'ishlangan. Malaka oshirish kurslarining asosiy maqsadi har bir tinglovchida uning ijodiy fikrlash qobiliyatiga ishonchini ta'minlash va o'rnatish, ularning ijodiy faoliyatini muntazam rag'batlantirishdan iborat. Maqolada andragogik ta'limning ahamiyati ta'kidlangan, chunki kattalar ta'limidagi pedagogik jarayon sub'ektlarning qiziqishlari va ehtiyojlaridan kelib chiqqan holda tashkil etilgan jarayon bo'lib, unda ta'lim maqsadlarining o'ziga xos darajasi va bilimlarni o'zlashtirishning amaliy jihati birlamchi mezon hisoblanadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *aralash ta'lim modeli, malaka oshirish kurslari, oliy ta'lim muassasalarining pedagog kadrlari, andragogik ta'lim, o'qitishning andragogik modeli, AKT, tinglovchi, sifatni oshirish, masofaviy ta'lim.*

УСЛОВИЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ

Гиясова Умида Эркиновна

преподаватель, Ташкентский государственный педагогический университет
имени Низами

umidagiyasova@rambler.ru

***Аннотация:** Статья посвящена анализу современных условий повышения качества образования в процессе повышения квалификации. Основная цель курсов повышения квалификации – обеспечить и утвердить у каждого обучающегося уверенность в своих способностях творчески мыслить, регулярно поощрять его творческую деятельность. В статье отмечается важность андрагогического образования, поскольку педагогический процесс в образовании взрослых представляет собой процесс, организованный исходя из интересов и потребностей субъектов, в котором первоочередно рассматриваются конкретный уровень образовательных целей и практический аспект критерий приобретения знаний.*

***Ключевые слова:** модель смешанного обучения, курсы повышения квалификации, педагогические кадры высших учебных заведений, андрагогическое образование, андрагогическая модель обучения, ИКТ, слушатель, повышение качества, дистанционное обучение.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, higher education institutions are engaged in retraining pedagogical personnel and creating a comfortable opportunity for trainees to think creatively, tolerantly accepting various opinions and ideas expressed by trainees, and promoting their activity in the educational process. The main goal of professional development courses is to ensure and establish confidence in each trainee about his/her ability to think creatively, to regularly encourage their creative activities as well.

Another unique aspect of the professional development process is the aspect related to the specific work experience and age categories of the subjects of education at this stage of education. In scientific-pedagogical analysis, educational subjects in the process of professional development are interpreted as andragogical age category.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Andragogy is considered a new direction of pedagogy – “Andragogy (from Greek aner, andros – adult male, ago – to lead) is a field of science that deals with the problems of lifelong education and upbringing of adults”.

In a broad sense, andragogy is a field of self-development of a person throughout his life, a network that helps adults to realize their abilities, opportunities and talents, to manifest their place and opportunities in life.

Researchers R. Ishmukhamedov and M. Mirsoliyeva explain that concepts such as “andragogy”, “andragogical education”, “andragogical model of teaching” have gained special importance in pedagogical terminology in recent years and explain its socio-pedagogical necessity as follows:

- the increase in the flow of information in the field of education, science and production as a result of scientific and technical progress;
- modern professional qualification requirements for personnel retraining and their professional development;
- the need to ensure interdisciplinary integration and harmony in educational processes;
- innovative educational environment and others.

According to the researchers' opinion, the pedagogical process in adult education is a process organized based on the interests and needs of subjects, in which the specific level of educational goals and the practical aspect of knowledge acquisition are considered as the primary criteria.

Therefore, it is appropriate to take into account the following peculiarities when defining the goals of andragogical education:

- individuality in the audience's social portrait (audience's social structure, age, socio-professional status, experience, expected results from training, interests) etc.
- the educational process is based not only on the professional, but also on the exchange of information in the social and household spheres, based on cooperative relations;
- trainee's independence, motivation to seek self-management, etc.

Therefore, andragogical education is considered a teaching model based on joint learning, cooperation, and communication relations of the organization of participants' knowledge and communicative activities, and in its organization, it is necessary to take into account the individuality of the subject of activity in a certain age-psycho-physiological and professional-social status.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The advantages of andragogical education are, first of all, the ability to concentrate the attention of the audience and keep it longer on a specific issue, and another advantage is the ability to present a relatively difficult issue to the audience without excessive explanations. Andragogical education is considered more complex

than other educational stages because it requires education that is higher than the stable knowledge, skills and competences that trainees already have.

In our opinion, it is possible to significantly increase the effectiveness of the educational process, which uses the possibilities of blended learning methodically.

It should be emphasized that one of the unique principles of the blended learning model is the variability and flexibility of the educational content. These principles make it possible to individualize the educational process and create the necessary pedagogical opportunities for self-development of the learner based on the variety of educational materials, tasks, control, assessment methods, independent work forms.

The implementation of the blended learning model requires the use of various digital educational resources and online services:

- learning management systems (LMS), for example, Moodle, Edmodo, etc.);
- digital collections of educational objects (unified collection of educational resources);
- online training courses (Mobile electronic school, etc.);
- instruments for creating and publishing educational content (constructive tests, 1C, etc.);
- instruments for feedback and communication (Mirapolis, Webinar, Skype, Google-chat, etc.);
- tools for cooperation (Google Docs, Word Online, etc.);
- tools for creating a collaborative community, communication platforms (social networks);
- tools for designing educational activities (electronic magazines, organizers).

The use of the blended learning model requires a special level of professional competence and training from the pedagogue. These are:

- ICT competence, the ability to use various electronic educational resources, the ability to work with online collaborative work, social networks and training systems;
- the ability to independently form educational content and resources in accordance with educational programs and educational goals;
- such as having the ability to differentiate the educational process based on the individual needs of each trainee.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thus, taking into account all the above mentioned, we can see that the psychological-pedagogical conditions for improving the quality and efficiency of education by implementing of the blended learning model are as follows:

- to transform the educational process from a monosubject to a polysubject paradigm, ensuring that education is oriented to individual needs, varied and flexible;
- focusing the educational process on the development of the individual trajectory of the person;

- achieving mutual harmony of traditional and electronic (distance) education elements in the educational process; flexibility of the learning model, availability of information, interactivity, temporal asynchrony and complementarity and consistency of teaching.

CONCLUSION

From the above points, it can be concluded that the implementation of the blended learning mechanisms in the development of professional competence of specialists, individuality, independent-creative development, as well as self-management, the ability to analyze their own creative solutions, the ability to develop independent thinking development, is important in ensuring continuity in self-professional and personal development.

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